

Full dataset		
<i>Body length</i>	Kruskal	0.05561
<i>Longest seta length</i>	Kruskal	0.0001
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.1056	0.4225
Extant:Eocene	0.5955	0.5955
Extant:Cretaceous	3.61e-05	0.0002
Miocene:Eocene	0.3392	0.6783
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.1645	0.4936
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.0085	0.0423
<i>Longest hastiseta length</i>	Kruskal	0.09
<i>Setae/Body ratio</i>	Kruskal	2.87e-05
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.0585	0.2693
Extant:Eocene	0.1669	0.3339
Extant:Cretaceous	2.18e-06	1.31e-05
Miocene:Eocene	0.7003	0.7003
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.1282	0.3847
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.0585	0.234
<i>Hastisetae/body ratio</i>	Kruskal	0.0028
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.2373	0.9492
Extant:Eocene	0.1654	0.8268
Extant:Cretaceous	0.0002	0.0013
Miocene:Eocene	0.8647	0.8647
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.2594	0.7781
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.3685	0.737

Without fragmented specimens		
<i>Body length</i>	Kruskal	0.0394
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.1592	0.6367
Extant:Eocene	0.0487	0.2434
Extant:Cretaceous	0.0052	0.0312
Miocene:Eocene	0.5647	1
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.5451	1
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.8716	0.8716
<i>Longest seta length</i>	Kruskal	0.0002
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.3183	0.955
Extant:Eocene	0.5046	1
Extant:Cretaceous	4.36e-05	0.0003
Miocene:Eocene	0.7779	0.7779
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.0646	0.2418
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.0247	0.1236
<i>Longest hastiseta length</i>	Kruskal	0.1857
<i>Setae/Body ratio</i>	Kruskal	2.85e-05
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.1195	0.3584
Extant:Eocene	0.1772	0.3544
Extant:Cretaceous	2.36e-06	1.41e-05
Miocene:Eocene	0.8595	0.8595
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.0837	0.3347
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.0499	0.2497
<i>Hastisetae/body ratio</i>	Kruskal	0.0009
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.6825	0.6825
Extant:Eocene	0.2028	0.8111
Extant:Cretaceous	0.0001	0.0007
Miocene:Eocene	0.5549	1
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.0892	0.4457
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.2448	0.7345

Megatominae		
<i>Body length</i>	Kruskal	0.0227
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.6047	1
Extant:Eocene	0.1503	0.4508
Extant:Cretaceous	0.0108	0.0645
Miocene:Eocene	0.1187	0.4746
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.0328	0.1642
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.8229	0.8229
<i>Longest seta length</i>	Kruskal	0.0004
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.0756	0.3022
Extant:Eocene	0.4442	0.8883
Extant:Cretaceous	5.07e-05	0.0003
Miocene:Eocene	0.2861	0.8582
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.8074	0.8074
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.043	0.2148
<i>Longest hastiseta length</i>	Kruskal	0.1337
<i>Setae/Body ratio</i>	Kruskal	4.36e-05
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.3647	0.7294
Extant:Eocene	0.2676	0.8027
Extant:Cretaceous	3.71e-06	2.23e-05
Miocene:Eocene	0.9575	0.9575
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.1461	0.5843
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.0398	0.1988
<i>Hastisetae/body ratio</i>	Kruskal	0.0015
Dunn test	uncorrected	corrected
Extant:Miocene	0.6657	0.6657
Extant:Eocene	0.1785	0.7139
Extant:Cretaceous	0.0002	0.001
Miocene:Eocene	0.5329	1
Miocene:Cretaceous	0.101	0.5052
Eocene:Cretaceous	0.2971	0.8912